

REALIZATION PATHS AND COUNTERMEASURES FOR FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHING QUALITY IMPROVEMENT: A NEW SYSTEMATIC MACROSCOPIC RESEARCH PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the paths and realization countermeasures for the future English teaching quality improvement, and revolves around the aspects of English teaching quality assessment after the introduction of the metaverse concept. By analyzing the interpretation of the metaverse concept and literature studies related to the application of metaverse technology by domestic and foreign scholars, we draw on the functional requirements analysis in the field of software design to construct the field of the future English teaching wisdom learning environment from a macroscopic and holistic perspective. In order to explore the relationship between the realization of English teaching quality in the context of future metaverse and quantitative analysis methods from a macro-system perspective, we also innovatively draw on the functional configuration theory of quality in marketing and construct a future English teaching quality assessment index system using English teaching in Chinese universities as an example. It is worth noting that the traditional index system is usually formed by the construction of teaching objects, teaching characteristics and lecture resources lecture characteristics and classroom nature, while the index system in this study is formed based on the field structure constructed in this paper, which is more universal from a macro perspective. In order to quantitatively evaluate the index system, we proposed a G1-entropy value method to calculate and rank the weights of the indexes and give targeted suggestions. We have achieved interdisciplinary theoretical reference, methodological improvement and quantitative-qualitative combination in this study. Via this study, we fill the gap in teaching quality assessment brought by the introduction of the future metaverse concept, propose innovations in the analysis of new concepts and improvement of old methods, build a new scenario of organic combination of new technology and traditional teaching, and provide a new way of thinking for future international and domestic educational research.

Keywords: Metaverse, teaching field architecture, English language teaching, teaching quality assessment, G1 method, entropy method, quality function deployment theory

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1. INTRODUCTION

In October 2019, China's Ministry of Education issued the "Implementation Opinions on the Construction of First-class Undergraduate Courses", which takes the reform and innovation of first-class undergraduate courses as the construction goal and implements the double 10,000 plan for first-class undergraduate courses. Among them, from 2019 to 2021, about 10,000 online first-class courses and online/offline hybrid first-class courses and about 15,000 national virtual simulation experimental teaching first-class courses are recommended to be recognized as national first-class undergraduate courses. In September 2020, the General Office of Education of China issued a notice on the work plan of "Online Retracing the Long March" and promoting "Four Histories" learning and education, which emphasizes the use of a new education model that organically combines online and offline, and online. In July 2020, China's Ministry of Education issued the "Opinions on Supporting the Healthy Development of New Industries and New Modes to Activate the Consumer Market and Drive Employment Expansion", proposing to support the integration of online and offline new industries and new modes as an important breakthrough in economic transformation and reform promotion. An important breakthrough in innovation is to promote the normalized integration of online and offline education, try to develop classroom teaching based on online intelligent environments, and form a high-quality online education resource supply. In January 2021, five departments of China's Ministry of Education, National Development and Reform Commission, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, Ministry of Finance, and State Administration of Radio and Television issued the Opinions on Vigorously Strengthening the Construction and Application of Online Education and Teaching Resources in Primary and Secondary Schools. The document proposes to basically form an online education platform system with clear positioning, interconnection and sharing by 2025, and to provide conditions to promote students' independent online learning habits and abilities from all aspects. Support. As well as the outline of the fourth session of China's 13th National People's Congress, the development goal of promoting the integration and innovation of information technology and the education field, such as promoting artificial intelligence, 5G and other modern information technology to help online teaching, was mentioned several times. With the rapid development of virtual reality technology, mixed reality technology, augmented reality technology and digital twin technology, especially virtual reality technology has been widely and deeply applied in many teaching disciplines in the past 20 years, for example, in geography, teachers show students the change process of various geographic phenomena through 3D technology to promote students' understanding, and in physical education, virtual space is used to complete sports activities that cannot be completed in real venues. In physical education, virtual space is used to accomplish sports activities that cannot be done in real venues. Thus, it can be seen that the enhancement of virtual reality technology has become frequently combined with the education and teaching industry, and whether a new education model and system will be formed in the future based on new technology and new ideas is a key topic worthy of the attention of international and domestic academic circles.

After the metaverse was proposed in 2020, it has caused extensive discussions in academia and industry, and most of the researches focus on the core technology aspects in the metaverse. The cloud universe is formed after the integration of virtual reality technology, mixed reality technology, augmented reality and other technologies mentioned above. Whether the introduction of the topic of metaverse in the future will form a new theory and technology in education and teaching is also a topic worth exploring. However, definitions of the concept of metaverse have so far varied. According to futurist Luke Shabro, a metaverse is a vague, digital hybrid reality with an irreplaceable and infinite project role that is not subject to traditional physical limitations and constraints. Dave Baszucki, CEO of Roblox, sees the metaverse as a 3D virtual world that connects everyone, where people have their own digital identities and can interact and create whatever they want in the world. Hackl, known as the godmother of the metaverse, believes that people can connect to everything around them in a virtual environment, from places to spaces and assets, and she sees the metaverse not just as virtual reality or immersive scenarios, but as a field with many converging physical and digital elements related to VR (virtual reality) hardware, spatial computing, and augmented reality hardware. While Zuckerberg believes that most tech companies are dedicated to building technologies that interact with users, the metaverse wants to build technologies that allow human interaction. Since the metaverse mostly focuses on emerging technologies and artificial intelligence, we have compiled interpretations of the metaverse concept from relevant experts, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Fig. 1 The six core technologies of the metaverse

The combination of metaverse and education may bring an unprecedented innovation to the education industry. Today's teaching is mostly conducted on a single scene, so the content of teaching will be relatively boring, but as soon as metaverse is added, education will have a great change. The introduction of VR devices can fully reshape the teaching content presentation and immerse students in knowledge, in addition, the plasticity of virtual space has also given rise to VR classrooms, virtual simulation training rooms, cloud collections and other scenarios, extending the teaching scene from the classroom. In addition, the plasticity of virtual space has also given rise to VR classrooms, virtual simulation training rooms, cloud collections and other scenarios, which extend the teaching scene from the classroom to the whole area, and learners will enter a new stage of "learning is life and life is learning". If teachers and students face to face in the classroom learning is the traditional one-dimensional form, teachers use multimedia classroom is two-dimensional, then VR and 3D interactive immersive classroom into a multi-

dimensional level, for example, learning planetary knowledge, put on VR glasses, the huge planets will appear in front of you, you can pull it far and close, clearly see its texture and characteristics. Secondly, practical training teaching is now mentioned to be more and more important in colleges and universities, with the application of metaverse can solve these real project practical training problems of high risk environment, high consumption and irreversibility, breaking through the experimental difficulties in traditional teaching. For example, architecture students are able to personally participate in building elevated bridges in cities through simulation labs, and the metaverse places more emphasis on the synergy between virtual space and real space, with virtual students and virtual teachers in the classroom, and supports the completion of multi-person interaction and collaboration scenarios in the same training space. Teachers engage in participatory training such as role-playing and event simulation in these scenarios, proactively solving complex teaching problems, making decisions, reflecting on actions, and collaborating with other participants in the teaching system, making the training activities more realistic, flexible, and sustainable. In addition, the virtual assistants in the metaverse have rich external images that learners can choose according to their personal preferences. Some studies show that virtual people are more attractive through expression changes and physical interactions, which can effectively stimulate learning motivation, reduce cognitive load and enhance learning efficacy. Even teaching interaction services and emotion regulation services can be used, that is, by developing virtual assistants can provide services for learning guidance, motivate learners and improve learning efficiency through emotion recognition and emotion regulation to motivate learners' positive emotions.

Based on the above background analysis, we sort out the contributions of this paper into the following three aspects. (1) An intelligent field architecture of ELT for the future metaverse is built. (2) Integrating the quality function deployment theory and the G1 entropy value method to conduct quantitative analysis. (3) Key indicators are found for the results of the quantitative analysis, and specific suggestions and recommendations are targeted.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Part 2 is a literature review, where we define the concept of educational metaverse, and specifically sort out three levels: application of metaverse concept, application of metaverse core technology in education industry, and quality assessment of educational teaching; Part 3 we give the technical roadmap of this paper's research; Part 4 we design a future intelligent English teaching field architecture based on metaverse; Part 5 In section 5, we introduce the quality function deployment theory and fuzzy mathematical theory; in section 6, we propose a future ELT quality assessment method considering the metaverse; in section 7, we present a case study, in which we take Chinese ELT as the research object for specific analysis; in section 8, we propose reform measures and suggestions for future ELT; and in section 9, we conclude the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The educational metaverse can be understood as the application of metaverse in education and teaching, which creates digital identities for teachers, students, administrators and other relevant personnel, opens up formal and informal teaching and learning venues in the virtual world, and allows teachers and students to interact and communicate in the virtual teaching and learning venues. Thinking about the metaverse from the perspective of educational philosophy, one can find that its most prominent empowering advantage is that it creates an immersive teaching and learning interactive field for teachers and students. The field of educational metaverse breaks the limitations of the physical world and creates a new virtual world through spatial virtual teaching, so that teachers and students can get the satisfaction of both real and virtual teaching needs in the physical and virtual worlds, which are in essence mutually influential, interconnected and co-developing. However, the virtual world in the education metaverse is not a simple replica of the physical world, nor is it a "parallel universe" of the physical world, but a redevelopment of the resources of the physical world. It is a kind of resource redevelopment of the physical world. Its media-enabling characteristics can

complement the deficiencies in the physical world, and even transcend the limitations of the physical world in some dimensions, forming a special educational metaverse field. In order to explore the application of metaverse in English teaching in this paper, we carry out a specific literature review from three aspects: application of metaverse concept, application of metaverse core technology in education teaching industry and quality assessment of education teaching, as follows.

In terms of applied research on the metaverse concept, since the concept of metaverse has been popular since 2020, the related research literature is currently lacking and the current research involves metaverse terms mainly in the field of artificial intelligence. Among them, Alpala et al [1] aim to improve collaboration and communication practices in 3D virtual worlds through VR and metaverse spaces focusing on the education and production sectors of smart factories, and they propose a framework structure for formal collaboration processes in virtual environments through VR-driven metaverse. Essentially, the framework structure built by their study also belongs to the category of metaverse field architecture, and we are grateful for their research ideas that provide methodological references for building the ELT field architecture in our present study. Jeong et al [2] proposed an innovative business model for a new e-commerce platform that overcomes the existing limitations of online shopping. Kliestik et al [3] contributed to the literature on retail business models in the metaverse environment by showing that cognitive artificial intelligence techniques and algorithms can play a pivotal role in the development of virtual commerce by enhancing the virtual shopping experience with data from location. What can be seen is that the integration and application of intelligent technologies in the metaverse can bring convenience to the development of many industries and likewise support the issue of teaching quality reform in our present study. Wu and Ho [4] explored the application of metaverse in emergency medicine by reviewing published studies and clinical management of patients. The results showed that the integration of augmented reality and virtual reality in the metaverse has a wide range of applications in education and clinical training. Sun et al [5] discussed the prospects of a metaverse data healthcare platform incorporating advanced artificial intelligence technologies in digital medicine and the future of the healthcare metaverse. Koo et al [6] proposed four propositions for metaverse tourism and suggested that tourism researchers begin to understand the metaverse tourism ecosystem. Škola et al [7] conducted a subjective and objective evaluation of an application that mixed an interactive virtual reality experience with 360-degree storytelling. The results suggest that EEG is a viable tool for future research on presence and immersion in interactive virtual reality. Pei et al [8] developed an interactive cognitive system to help learn the structural system of ancient Chinese architecture to study the effects of applying HCI concepts in learning. The results showed that integrating VR and interactive learning games could improve students' positive attitudes and learning outcomes towards ancient Chinese architecture. Zhang et al [9] explored the use of metaverse concepts in cultural heritage applications and proposed a framework for a cultural heritage metaverse to construct a cultural heritage metaverse with complex and dynamic properties that can be used for different applications, including heritage conservation. Buhalis et al [10] conducted a comprehensive literature review analyzing the early applications of metaverse in hospitality and tourism, defining and conceptualizing the potential of metaverse for customer experience and value co-creation in the hospitality industry. Several of the aforementioned studies, richly introduced that metaverse can be applied in the future to multidisciplinary fields such as medicine, tourism, architecture, non-heritage preservation, hospitality management, etc., is a finding that we consider very interesting, regarding the applications of metaverse that have already spread to many fields and are likewise a must in future pedagogical development. Pamucar et al [11] considered four alternative metaverse that can transition transportation systems to meta metaverse worlds and demonstrated their efficacy through case studies. Cruz-Lara et al [12] used a multilingual information framework to develop

a multilingual assisted chat interface to simplify communication and language learning in a metaverse virtual world, offering new possibilities for learning foreign languages. We highly recognize the relevant application results about the metaverse concept, which provide us with reference for the future metaverse context of English teaching quality assessment proposed in this study. What can be seen is that most of the results of the current research on the metaverse concept only focus on one technology, such as VR technology, Internet of Things technology, blockchain technology, etc., which, although practically corroborates the feasibility of future metaverse development, few studies have been conducted from The overall perspective of building an intelligent architecture based on metaverse under the industry domain.

In terms of research on the application of metaverse core technologies in the education and teaching industry, researchers in recent years have experimented with various ways of trying to introduce metaverse into teaching and learning activities to verify its positive effects in education and teaching. marini et al [13] study aimed to reveal the efficacy of mobile augmented reality learning media with metaverse on improving student learning outcomes in science classes, and their findings found that students who used the metaverse Kanematsu et al. [14] used Metaverse to conduct a hybrid of e-learning and hands-on activities for education and demonstrated the effectiveness of this method in improving the quality of teaching and learning. education with e-learning and hands-on activities. Lee et al [15] applied the fuzzy ontology concept of the Heart Sutra to artificial intelligence for young students to learn and experience computational intelligence applications on a metaverse platform and the results showed an upward trend in learners' performance in the learning content. lo and Tsai [16] proposed a novel metaverse 3D virtual reality architecture to facilitate water education using modern information technology. The results of the experiment showed that participants showed significant improvements in learning various aspects of environmental conservation concepts. Reyes [17] analyzed the perceptions of upper-middle class students in a private educational institution in Mexico regarding an augmented reality teaching strategy based on a metaverse mobile application. The results showed that the application of augmented reality in mathematics instruction significantly benefited student performance. Celik and Yangın Ersanlı [18] examined EFL learners' attitudes toward the use of augmented reality technology. The results showed that the use of AR-based mobile applications improved learners' language performance and that learners had positive attitudes toward the use of augmented reality. It is clear from their studies that although they all introduced metaverse technology through different forms of instructional models, their experiments provide strong evidence for the effectiveness of metaverse technology in enhancing teaching and learning. Since the model of metaverse teaching has not yet taken shape, many researchers are still working on how to better integrate metaverse into teaching and learning. The main objective of Lee et al [15] was to bring pioneering insights into the core lines of sustainable education research by investigating the multidimensional preparedness of faculty in designing technology-enhanced learning environments. Araya et al [19] provided information on the use of interactive learning in a database course in an integrated environment of physical space and virtual immersion space. The results suggest the feasibility of replicating this experience in other courses and majors. Belei et al [20] integrated a metaverse into an undergraduate brand management course, providing a suitable means to promote students' understanding of branding theory concepts and the ability to apply them to real-life scenarios, offering a promising approach to bridging the classroom gap between branding theory and practice. Lee and Hwang [21] investigated how virtual reality creation of English digital textbooks for English teachers could be linked to learning adaptations and metaverse platforms and used as a tool to achieve sustainable education by investigating teachers' multidimensional readiness to design technology-enhanced learning environments. Wagner et al [22] used technology through metaverse distance education courses and MOOCs for students in vocational courses provide support for programs

to be able to contribute to the content in a more dynamic environment. Makransky and Mayer [23] described and investigated the principles of immersion in multimedia learning. The results show that immersion programs can have a positive longitudinal impact on learning. Yu [24] takes as a starting point the specific application of metaverse spatial technology in sports, providing basic data showing the direction of metaverse-based physical education, contributing to the expansion of the scope and depth of subsequent research. Their studies all point to the metaverse space, which integrates physical space and virtual immersion space, as a key to facilitate the development of teaching and learning, providing learners with more direct access to learning, making it easier for learners to understand the content and better grasp how to apply their knowledge. Tarouco et al. discuss and describe the implementation of a virtual learning laboratory for teaching calculus in engineering courses, integrating in the metaverse a learning object for teaching calculus, providing students with a collaborative, interactive, and dynamic learning environment that improves the quality of learning. Liu and Zhang [25] discuss and describe the application of virtual communities in a metaverse for foreign language learning providing learners with an improved and favorable learning environment. In other words, virtual spaces provide learners with a superior learning environment than traditional teaching classrooms. Kanematsu et al [26] conducted virtual problem-oriented learning in a metaverse with students from some Japanese national technical colleges, and all results were studied from the perspective of the effectiveness of engineering design and STEM education. Kye et al [27] examined augmented reality, recorded life, mirror world, and virtual reality by giving an example of the application of augmented reality technology in medical education. These four types of metaverse spaces are illustrated in terms of their potential and limitations in educational applications. Although metaverse teaching is a newborn teaching method, its potential is being explored by everyone indefinitely, and through this paper we hope to make indispensable new discoveries for the future quality improvement of metaverse English teaching.

In order to promote the development of education and teaching quality assessment, we need to establish different evaluation criteria according to the needs of educational innovation in order to achieve the purpose of promoting teaching quality improvement. Spiel et al [28] proposed a different five-stage evaluation method focusing on the first stage of medical curriculum system evaluation, described several challenges of this evaluation method, and illustrated the strategies used to overcome these. Li [29] constructed an evaluation system of graduate mental health education based on the graduate mental health education system, which consists of six first-level indicators and thirty twenty indicators, and individual indicators can be adjusted according to practical applications to improve the scientificity of evaluation results. Fan et al [30] analyzed the factors affecting the quality of entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities from a theoretical perspective, established an evaluation index system and fuzzy evaluation model to evaluate entrepreneurship education. Liu and Wang [31] analyzed the current situation and influencing factors of teaching quality evaluation, established the evaluation index system of teaching quality in colleges and universities and conducted an empirical study, taking economics and management majors as an example. The study promoted the teaching quality of economic management majors in colleges and universities from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Kang and Yan [32] analyzed the influencing factors from four aspects: entrepreneurship education concept, entrepreneurship education teachers and research, entrepreneurship education curriculum and activities, and entrepreneurship education environment in colleges and universities, and constructed a specific evaluation index system and model. CHEN et al [33] proposed the evaluation principles of innovation education in colleges and universities, and the established principles of innovation evaluation system. and analyzed the established principles of innovation evaluation system and selected evaluation indexes and methods, which provided the basis and experience for the evaluation of the results of innovation education in colleges and universities.

These studies have constructed new evaluation indexes in medical education, entrepreneurship education, mental health education and economic management teaching respectively, which provide more directional guidance to improve the quality of education and teaching from several aspects. In addition to evaluation indexes, a number of researchers have proposed new education quality evaluation systems by analyzing the existing evaluation systems. Dong et al [34] introduced engineering education accreditation and its education quality evaluation methods, and analyzed and summarized the advantages of these methods. With the purpose of continuous quality improvement and achieving educational goals, a multi-dimensional education quality evaluation system for engineering masters was proposed. Yu [35] discussed the evaluation system of rural legal education in terms of connotation, function and methods. Zhang and Yu [36] analyzed the principles of constructing a modern distance education teaching quality evaluation system based on the overview of modern distance education. A quality evaluation system adapted to the modern distance education system was established to promote the new development of education in China. xu et al [37] formed a problem-oriented education quality dynamic evaluation system based on realistic requirements. And a specific case of quality evaluation of problem-oriented learning education for engineering practice in universities is discussed using this fuzzy evaluation method. Through prior research, we note that many researchers have used fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method in establishing or analyzing teaching quality evaluation system, while Jin et al [38] explored the effectiveness of using fuzzy comprehensive evaluation to evaluate teachers' teaching quality. Shuang [39] provided a fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method to solve the education quality evaluation problem, and then illustrated the ideological and political education quality framework of the evaluation system and proved the validity of the method through experimental results. It can be seen that the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method is very important in the education quality evaluation system, and its effectiveness has been verified many times. In order to construct new evaluation indexes and systems more effectively, we must make a deeper understanding and analysis of the past evaluation methods and the future development direction. Zhang and Xu [40] reviewed the development of higher education education teaching evaluation and proposed that the impact of the big data era on higher education will create innovation in all aspects of education. Liu [41], based on the development and practice of physical education teaching evaluation, analyzed the objects, methods and standards of current physical education teaching evaluation in China. It also analyzed the main problems in current physical education evaluation and predicted its reform and future development trend. He and Yin [42] summarized a new evaluation system that is more relevant and practical in the process of teaching English in college according to the specific situation of college English teaching. li and Sun [43] proposed a new evaluation system based on cloud computing.] proposed a model for evaluating the quality of English speaking teaching based on cloud computing. The experimental results show that the model can effectively evaluate the quality of English speaking teaching. The cloud-based ELT evaluation model also points to the fact that we are constantly developing teaching methods supported by science and technology, which means that adding the support of science and technology to the teaching quality evaluation will make the evaluation system better. Zhang et al [44] conducted teaching quality evaluation in the framework of machine learning, using artificial neural network model as the main model to describe the substantive principles of teaching quality. Barry et al [45] introduced an incarnational blink system in a problem-based virtual learning class in Metaverse, using which the teacher could well analyze the students' responses for better results in virtual learning.

In general, the current research related applications on metaverse education teaching and quality assessment classes are relatively abundant, but we can see by combing through the existing related literature that few studies have built the field architecture from a macroscopic and holistic perspective, which is an essential link in the future metaverse applications. Most of the current studies only focus on a single technology or an integrated application of several technologies, so we will propose in this paper to build the field architecture from the perspective of macro overall technology application in order to facilitate further analysis of some essential features related to education and teaching in the future. With regard to the assessment of the quality of teaching and learning, the existing studies have been based on the essential characteristics of teaching and learning to construct the index system. Unlike traditional methods of constructing indicator systems, the idea of constructing indicator systems in this study comes from the structure of the field we have built. Therefore, the index system we constructed in this article is also universal, and it is not only applicable to the English teaching we are going to study, but also to the teaching of physical education, history, biology, and many other subjects. In terms of assessment methods, most of the existing studies focus on fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method. The core idea of the G1 entropy method that we use in this study is also the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method. However, unlike the existing evaluation ideas, we introduce the identity information weight of experts in the evaluation process to improve the quality of the evaluation and the reliability of the evaluation results. This is one of the existing studies that we have not found any relevant studies that have adopted such a research perspective.

3 FUTURE INTELLIGENT ENGLISH TEACHING FIELD ARCHITECTURE DESIGN: FROM VIRTUAL REALITY TO METAVERSE

3.1. Scene structure design based on virtual reality technology

Fig.2 Virtual reality technology scene structure design for future metaverse English teaching

3.2 Metaverse-based intelligent field architecture design

Fig.3 Intelligent field architecture design for future metaverse English teaching

3.3. Analysis of the differences between metaverse English teaching and English teaching based on virtual reality technology

According to Figure 3 above, we further sort out the following differences between the built up metaverse English teaching field structure and traditional English education.

1. The teaching content of the metaverse English teaching model is richer, including not only a single textbook, but also standard real-life pronunciation, practical application scenarios teaching, interactive scenarios with diplomacy, etc. There is a more powerful knowledge base, relying on natural language processing and artificial intelligence with its own intellectual property rights of multi-dimensional analysis.
2. Virtual reality can bring learners a sense of immersion and presence that is unmatched by traditional educational media, and can greatly increase the knowledge conversion rate. Panoramic images can make learners feel like they are in their native language environment and communicate face-to-face with native English speakers. The vivid scenario-based learning allows students to have a deeper understanding of how spoken English is actually used in reality, and improves learning efficiency. Traditional English teaching focuses on formulaic repetition and memorization to improve mastery of the language through mandatory indoctrination. The metaverse English teaching model, however, focuses more on the cultivation of interest and practical application, and is a deeper restoration of English as a language environment.
3. In metaverse classroom teaching, comprehensive insight into teaching behavior can be gained through AI analysis, comprehensive evaluation of classroom behavior, and classroom review with evaluation data for teachers to provide personalized teaching reference, which helps to improve teachers' development. It can also provide data support for students' future development by analyzing their development tendencies.
4. More flexible and intelligent teaching methods. In traditional English teaching, each student's learning content is synchronized and almost undifferentiated. To achieve better teaching results and meet the diverse needs of students, more teachers are needed in traditional English teaching. But in the metaverse English teaching model, personalized teaching can be achieved easily, efficiently and cost-effectively through human-computer interaction.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Quality Function Deployment

The concept of QFD (Quality Function Deployment) was first put forward by YO JI AKAO, a Japanese researcher on product quality risk management. There are many types of QFD translation in international academic research. The representative translations generally recognized by Chinese scholars are: quality function deployment theory, quality function deployment, quality function deployment and house of quality. Although the concept of QFD comes from the field of product quality management, QFD has been widely used in many disciplines and social applications, such as system risk assessment, engineering quality management, enterprise strategic management, infrastructure design and so on. By tracing back to the initial start and development research process of QFD, the main core idea of QFD is to analyze customer needs, focus on customer demand objectives, study the correlation between needs and realization ways and the competitive relationship between needs, and finally output the evaluation results of customer demand importance through quality evaluation theory and technology. This method actually builds a "house" in the evaluation system of system management science, and realizes the specific customized demand scenario inside the "house". The specific structure of the house is shown in Figure 4 below.

In short, the quality function deployment theory is based on "customer demand (or customer problem) - implementation method (or technical means) - relationship matrix between demand and approach - quantifiable evaluation and analysis method". Its core idea is demand splitting and importance ranking. The specific operation process is to input customer demand purpose and information elements through targeted construction of house of quality structure model, Then use the quantifiable method to output the demand results and realize the ranking analysis of the importance of demand factors, so as to transform the actual needs of customers into specific production plans that can be implemented.

Fig.4 General formal framework of house of quality

1. Left wall: represents the input matrix, representing customer needs and characteristic elements, which can generally be obtained through social investigation.

2. Ceiling: represents the HOWS matrix, which indicates how to do according to the technical requirements, that is, the quantifiable technical methods and measures obtained from the demand transformation.

3. Room: represents the correlation matrix, describing the relationship between customer needs and the technical ways to realize this demand.

4. Roof: represents the HOWS correlation matrix, which represents the analysis of the correlation between requirements and technology.

5. Right wall: represents the results of the evaluation matrix, which refers to competitive or feasibility analysis and comparison, and evaluates the market competitiveness from the perspective of customer needs.

6. Basement: represents how to output the evaluation result matrix, which represents the application of quantifiable technical methods to realize customer needs and the ranking results of the importance relationship between customer demand factors.

In recent years, more and more scholars have started to use QFD theory to study real-life problems in the field of education and management. For example, Akundi, A et al. used quality function theory to conduct a well-organized anonymous survey on different aspects of a course, and the study extracted several key findings about curriculum improvement, students' expectations, and technical skills development from the students' perspective. Yang, Y and Zhou, W proposed a quality function unfolding (QFD) theory-based Haiyun, C et al. used QFD multidimensional analysis of innovation strategies for green supply chain management to provide recommendations for customer relationship management in energy companies, and understanding customer expectations through customer relationship management is the most important. The study by Karanjekar et al. focused on the technical institution as a service provider and students as the main stakeholders, using QFD as a theoretical model to conduct a

relevant study. the study by Cetinkaya, C et al. applied the quality function unfolding (QFD) method to the educational curriculum of the industrial engineering department in Gaziantep and the results were The results were analyzed. It can be seen that the QFD method is valuable in the field of pedagogy and that QFD is advanced and cutting-edge as a method used for systemic analysis. Therefore, we will draw on the quality funtion deployment theory in this study to logically and quantitatively analyze the quality assessment of English language teaching in the future-oriented metaverse and to improve the overall logic and readability.

4.2. Fuzzy mathematics theory: G1 entropy method

The G1 method is a subjective weighting method based on the improvement of the traditional AHP method. It can not only meet the requirements of the consistency test, but also avoid the disadvantages of large amount of calculation, many calculation processes and inaccurate results in the AHP method. It is suitable for the calculation of indicator weights at the same level. Fig. 3 shows the steps for calculating indicator weights using the G1 method.

Fig.5 Weighting process by G1 method

In Fig. 5, n is the number of indicators; w_k is the weight of the k th indicator; $r_k = \frac{w_{k-1}}{w_k}$ is the ratio of the importance of the previous indicator to the next indicator. The specific assignment of r_k is shown in Table 2

Table 1 Assignment reference table r_k

Outcomes	Description
1.0	Indicator $k-1$ is as important as indicator k
1.2	Indicator $k-1$ is slightly more important than indicator k
1.4	Indicator $k-1$ is apparently more important than indicator k
1.6	Indicator $k-1$ is strongly important compared to indicator k
1.8	Indicator $k-1$ is extremely important compared to indicator k

Further, the weight of the indicator can be determined according to the following steps:

The product r_i can be obtained according to $\prod_i^m r_i$:

$$\prod_i^m r_i = \frac{w_{i-1}}{w_i} \times \frac{w_i}{w_{i+1}} \times \dots \times \frac{w_{m-1}}{w_m} = \frac{w_{i-1}}{w_m} \quad (1)$$

And then $\sum_{i=2}^m (\prod_i^m r_i)$:

$$\sum_{i=2}^m (\prod_i^m r_i) = \sum_{i=2}^m \frac{w_{i-1}}{w_m} = \frac{1}{w_m} (\sum_{i=1}^m w_i - w_m) \quad (2)$$

Since the total weight cannot exceed 1, there is $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1$, and formula 1 can be converted into:

$$\sum_{i=2}^m (\prod_i^m r_i) = \sum_{i=2}^m \frac{w_{i-1}}{w_m} = \frac{1}{w_m} (\sum_{i=1}^m w_i - w_m) = \frac{1}{w_m} - 1 \quad (3)$$

Finally, the weight value of the m index can be obtained w_m :

$$w_m = (1 + \sum_{i=2}^m \prod_i^m r_i)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

According to the value w_m , then to calculate $m-1$, $m-2$, ..., 3, 2 weight value, $w_{i-1} = r_i w_i$, $i=m, m-1, m-2, \dots, 3, 2$; w_{i-1} represents $i-1$ weight, w_i resents i .

The entropy value method in the objective weighting method is used to objectively assign the decision indicator. It calculates the information entropy of the indicator and determines the weight of the decision indicator according to the relative change degree of the indicator on the system as a whole. The larger the relative change degree, the higher the weight. The steps to determine the indicator weight by the entropy method are as follows:

Step 1: Data normalization

Since there are differences in the dimension and order of magnitude in the evaluation indicators, it is necessary to eliminate the influence of different dimensions on the evaluation results. First, the maximum and minimum methods are used to normalize the indicators.

$$c_i = \frac{x_i^{\max} - x_i}{x_i^{\max} - x_i^{\min}} \quad (5)$$

where c_i is the normalized value of the indicator; $x_i^{\max}$ is the maximum value of the i th indicator; $x_i^{\min}$ is the minimum value of the i th indicator; x_i is the value of the i th indicator.

Step 2: Determine information entropy and information utility value

The information utility value I_i of an indicator depends on the difference between the information entropy E_i of the indicator and 1. The larger the difference is, the greater the information utility value and the greater the weight.

$$E_i = -\frac{1}{\ln n} \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \ln p_i \quad (6)$$

$$p_i = \frac{c_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i} \quad (7)$$

$$I_i = 1 - E_i \quad (8)$$

Step 3: Determine the weight value of each decision indicator

Calculating the weight value of an indicator by the entropy method is to use the information value of the indicator for calculation. The higher the value, the greater the importance of the evaluation.

$$G_i = \frac{I_i}{\left(n - \sum_{i=1}^n E_i\right)} \quad (9)$$

$$w_i = \frac{G_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n G_i} \quad (10)$$

To sum up, in this study, we use as the subjective weight of the indicator and as the objective weight of the indicator, so the comprehensive weight is determined by linear weighting as follows:

$$Z = \frac{w_m w_j}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_m w_j} \quad (11)$$

5 A FUTURE APPROACH TO ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING CONSIDERING A METAVERSE

5.1. Designing a Quality House Structure for Future ELT Assessment

We design the QFD-based quality house structure model for future ELT assessment based on the basic theory of quality house in Section 5.1, as shown in Figure 6 below.

Fig.6 Schematic diagram of the structure of future ELT assessment based on QFD

5.2 Flowchart of Future English Teaching Quality Assessment of Consider Universe

In order to facilitate the smooth development of the subsequent study, we combed the QFD theoretical framework and the structure of the future English teaching assessment framework based on QFD, and we sorted out the process schematic of the future-oriented metaverse English teaching quality assessment to be carried out in this paper, as shown in Figure 7 below.

Fig.7 Schematic diagram of the design process of the future metaverse English teaching quality assessment

6. CASE STUDY: RESEARCH EVIDENCE FROM ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN CHINA

6.1. Future English teaching quality assessment index system construction

(1) Principles of index system construction

In the face of the quality assessment problem of future English teaching, the index system of factors affecting the quality of future English teaching should be constructed in such a way that it can intuitively reflect the specific development of future English teaching characteristics, especially the characteristics of the metaverse English teaching. This determines that in the process of constructing the indicators, we must follow systematicity and comprehensiveness, scientificity and practicality, clarity and wholeness, comparability and operability, as follows.

(i) Systematic and comprehensiveness.

Systematic and comprehensiveness means that the indicators of the future-oriented English teaching quality influencing factors should be unified and conform to the teaching characteristics. In this study, we investigate and analyze the factors of teaching characteristics, students' perceptions, teachers' perceptions, distance learning characteristics and online technology characteristics in a unified and comprehensive manner.

(ii) Scientificity and practicality.

Scientific and practicality means that the evaluation indicators can transform some conceptual contents into indicators that can be visually compared and quantitatively evaluated. The evaluation indexes need to be based on scientific and systematic in-depth investigation and analysis of the whole future English teaching situation, and through the analysis, we can conclude that those indexes are affecting the quality of English teaching.

(iii) Clarity and wholeness.

The principle of clarity and wholeness is to make specific requirements for the system of indicators affecting the quality of future English teaching. The most important thing is to consider the directly related factors as a whole for integration, and the guidelines and classification of indicators based on their specific attributes must be clear and reasonable, and there is no crossover between the structures, and we are classifying them in this study according to the principle of hierarchical classification of three-level indicators.

(iv) Comparability and operability.

The purpose of this indicator system constructed is to explore the key factors for the future improvement of English teaching quality, to use the existing resources as much as possible, and to adopt similarity alternatives for the inaccessible relevant resources to ensure the operability of the indicators. At the same time, in the process of constructing the index factors, there needs to be differences between the indicators in the horizontal comparison.

(2) Methodology of index system construction

In our study, we analyzed through theoretical and practical analysis, according to the requirements of the policy document "Deepening the General Program of Education Evaluation Reform in the New Era" issued by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council of China, and conducted further through expert consultation interviews, further through actual research interviews with experts in related fields. Then it was clarified that the indicator system we constructed is composed of 1 primary indicator, 5 secondary indicators and 23 tertiary indicators.

(3) Specific structure of the index system

The specific structure of the index system is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 The structure of the index system of factors influencing the quality of future-oriented English teaching

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Description of the meaning of the three levels of indicators
Assessment of factors influencing the quality of future-oriented English language teaching A_1	Instructional Characteristics Factors B_{11}	Form of English teaching activities C_{111}	Provide students with appropriate English teaching contexts according to the teaching requirements and the process of knowledge acquisition by students
		English Teaching Structure C_{112}	Overall English knowledge framework
		English classroom atmosphere C_{113}	Atmosphere between English teachers and students and between students and students
		English Teaching Content C_{114}	English language skills, language knowledge, emotional attitudes, learning strategies and cultural awareness
		English Teaching Methods C_{115}	Principles and methods for guiding and facilitating students' effective learning of English
		English Teaching Environment C_{116}	The creation and arrangement of English learning environment
	Student perception factors B_{12}	Student perception factors C_{121}	Students' ability to learn English independently, initiative, and independent thinking
		Willingness to continue learning English C_{122}	Students' interest and willingness to continue learning English
		English Learning Satisfaction C_{123}	Teachers' ELT competence, learning support, perceived technology ease of use, self-efficacy, perceived technology usefulness, and motivation to learn
		English Co-learning C_{124}	English escort language partner, group learning, opinion exchange, communication and interaction
	Teacher perception factors B_{13}	Analysis of English teaching behavior C_{131}	English classroom management behavior, teaching introduction behavior, teacher-student interaction
		English Teaching Evaluation C_{132}	Students' sense of participation, spirit of cooperation, knowledge understanding and cognitive level, ability to analyze and investigate problems, and skills of expression and communication
		English Teaching Design C_{133}	English teaching objectives, teaching strategies, teaching evaluation, task analysis
		After-school English tutoring C_{134}	Teaching English to students according to their abilities and patiently answering questions
	Distance learning characteristic factors B_{14}	Personalized English Learning C_{141}	English interest development, uniqueness, multi-level assessment, and mind expansion
		Strong interactivity in English C_{142}	Human-English learning system interaction, self-interaction, interpersonal interaction

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Description of the meaning of the three levels of indicators
		Diversification of English learning scenarios C_{143}	English language environment provision, online communicative scenarios, emotional interaction enhancement, output ability development
		Flexible English teaching C_{144}	Cross-regional, cross-cultural, cross-temporal
	Online technical characteristics factors B_{15}	ELT Information Presentation C_{151}	Virtual Simulation English Teaching Resources
		English Teaching Context Creation C_{152}	English language practice scenarios provided
		English teaching process optimization C_{153}	Online and offline virtual reality, intelligent English teaching management
		English independent creativity C_{154}	Teaching practices task-oriented, immersive exploration of English self-study
		English Resource Integration C_{155}	English Teaching Resources Sharing

6.2 Calculating the Importance of Future English Teaching Quality Assessment Indicators

(1) Method of calculating the weight value of expert identity information

The original decision evaluation data of the G1-entropy value method used in this study is obtained from the experts' scores, and the experts' credibility criteria are judged from five aspects of the experts' length of service, education, profession, experience and title, and the specific criteria weights are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Expert scoring criteria weighting table

Factors	Weight r_i	Level	Score s
Working years	3	>30	0.8
		15~30	0.6
		<15	0.4
Education	2	PH.D	0.8
		Master	0.6
		Bachelor	0.4
Major	2	Economics	0.8
		Social Science	0.6
		Management	0.4
Experience	2	Experience in teaching English	0.8
		No experience in teaching English	0.4
Title	1	Professor	0.8
		Associate Professor	0.6
		Lecture	0.4

The reliability of experts can be calculated according to the expert weight scoring table 4. The reliability calculation formula of experts is as follows:

$$R_e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 r_i s}{10} \quad (11)$$

According to the expert reliability calculation formula (11), the weight of experts can be further calculated as follows:

$$w_e = \frac{R_e}{\sum_{e=1}^n R_e} \tag{12}$$

(2) Calculation method of the four weights

1. Calculation of expert weight values

We found five experts from four universities, Guangdong Second Normal College, Huizhou College, South China Normal University, and Sun Yat-sen University, to score the importance of the indexes in our study of the quality assessment of English teaching in the future-oriented metaverse 5 experts were found, and the identity information of the five experts is shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4 Identification information sheet for 5 experts

No.	Working years	Education	Major	Experience	Title
1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
2	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.8
3	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.6
4	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.6
5	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.4

With the above credibility and weight value calculation formulas, we can derive the expert weight calculation results as shown in Table 5 below, and the weight and credibility values in Table 5 are retained to three decimal places.

Table 5 Table of calculation results of identification information of 5 experts

No.	Reliability R_e	Weight w_e
1	0.800	0.247
2	0.760	0.235
3	0.720	0.222
4	0.500	0.154
5	0.460	0.142

2. G1 method weight value calculation

According to the calculation rules of the G1 method in part 5.2, we ranked and assigned values to the above 23 indicators by the subjective assignment of 5 experts, and the subjective assignment ranking of 5 experts is shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6 Preliminary importance ranking table of indicators by 5 experts

No.	Preliminary Importance Ranking
1	$C_{114} f C_{133} f C_{115} f C_{121} f C_{131} f C_{154} f C_{143} f C_{152} f C_{153} f C_{112} f C_{124} f C_{132} f C_{141} f C_{122} f C_{116} f C_{111} f C_{142} f C_{123} f C_{155} f C_{144} f C_{151} f C_{134} f C_{113}$
2	$C_{131} f C_{133} f C_{121} f C_{114} f C_{154} f C_{115} f C_{152} f C_{112} f C_{143} f C_{153} f C_{141} f C_{124} f C_{116} f C_{132} f C_{122} f C_{142} f C_{111} f C_{123} f C_{134} f C_{144} f C_{155} f C_{151} f C_{113}$
3	$C_{121} f C_{131} f C_{114} f C_{154} f C_{133} f C_{115} f C_{153} f C_{112} f C_{152} f C_{124} f C_{132} f C_{143} f C_{141} f C_{122} f C_{123} f C_{142} f C_{155} f C_{116} f C_{111} f C_{144} f C_{13} f C_{151} f C_{134}$
4	$C_{143} f C_{133} f C_{154} f C_{131} f C_{121} f C_{115} f C_{132} f C_{152} f C_{124} f C_{114} f C_{112} f C_{153} f C_{141} f C_{111} f C_{122} f C_{142} f C_{116} f C_{123} f C_{155} f C_{113} f C_{144} f C_{134} f C_{151}$
5	$C_{121} f C_{154} f C_{143} f C_{115} f C_{131} f C_{133} f C_{153} f C_{112} f C_{132} f C_{152} f C_{114} f C_{124} f C_{122} f C_{111} f C_{123} f C_{141} f C_{116} f C_{142} f C_{144} f C_{134} f C_{155} f C_{151} f C_{113}$

According to the assignment rules and results in Table 1, we organized the raw data of G1 method assignments of five experts as shown in Tables 11 to 15 in the Appendix.

According to the G1 method weight calculation formula (1), the G1 method calculation results of 23 tertiary indicators can be obtained as shown in Table 7 below.

Table 7 Table of weight calculation results of 5 experts on G1 method

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5
A_1	B_{11}	C_{111}	0.019	0.033	0.027	0.057	0.051
		C_{112}	0.099	0.236	0.225	0.122	0.193
		C_{113}	0.009	0.021	0.022	0.023	0.014
		C_{114}	0.500	0.368	0.431	0.143	0.106
		C_{115}	0.391	0.290	0.294	0.255	0.368
		C_{116}	0.023	0.081	0.029	0.036	0.031
	B_{12}	C_{121}	0.348	0.412	0.500	0.308	0.500
		C_{122}	0.034	0.043	0.072	0.048	0.066
		C_{123}	0.016	0.030	0.050	0.031	0.043
		C_{124}	0.099	0.096	0.181	0.178	0.084
	B_{13}	C_{131}	0.276	0.500	0.455	0.367	0.327
		C_{132}	0.078	0.056	0.155	0.222	0.146
		C_{133}	0.455	0.476	0.368	0.455	0.272
		C_{134}	0.009	0.030	0.018	0.018	0.020
	B_{14}	C_{141}	0.053	0.121	0.099	0.083	0.039
		C_{142}	0.017	0.036	0.042	0.040	0.026
		C_{143}	0.137	0.236	0.133	0.500	0.412
		C_{144}	0.012	0.028	0.024	0.020	0.021
	B_{15}	C_{151}	0.011	0.021	0.020	0.016	0.015
		C_{152}	0.126	0.254	0.195	0.192	0.125
		C_{153}	0.107	0.181	0.243	0.112	0.223
		C_{154}	0.193	0.346	0.431	0.410	0.476
		C_{155}	0.013	0.023	0.035	0.026	0.016

Based on the data in Table 7 combined with the expert credibility and weight calculation results in Table 5, the G1 method weight results of the indicators can be finally calculated, as shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8 Table of final calculation results of G1 method

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Calculation results of the final weight value of G1 method
A_1	B_{11}	C_{111}	0.034
		C_{112}	0.176
		C_{113}	0.018
		C_{114}	0.343
		C_{115}	0.322
		C_{116}	0.041
	B_{12}	C_{121}	0.412
		C_{122}	0.051
		C_{123}	0.033
		C_{124}	0.127
	B_{13}	C_{131}	0.390
		C_{132}	0.122
		C_{133}	0.415
		C_{134}	0.019
	B_{14}	C_{141}	0.082
C_{142}		0.032	
C_{143}		0.254	
C_{144}		0.021	
B_{15}	C_{151}	0.017	
	C_{152}	0.181	
	C_{153}	0.172	
	C_{154}	0.355	
	C_{155}	0.023	

3. Entropy value method weight value calculation

According to equation (2) to equation (6), the results of entropy method weights of indicators can be calculated as shown in Table 9 below.

Table 9 Entropy method weight value calculation results table

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Information entropy of the indicator	Information utility value of the indicator	Entropy method weight value calculation results
A_1	B_{11}	C_{111}	0.009	0.991	0.045
		C_{112}	0.046	0.954	0.043
		C_{113}	0.001	0.999	0.045
		C_{114}	0.070	0.930	0.042
		C_{115}	0.070	0.930	0.042
		C_{116}	0.011	0.989	0.045
	B_{12}	C_{121}	0.081	0.919	0.041
		C_{122}	0.015	0.985	0.044
		C_{123}	0.008	0.992	0.045
		C_{124}	0.036	0.964	0.043
	B_{13}	C_{131}	0.078	0.922	0.042
		C_{132}	0.034	0.966	0.044
		C_{133}	0.081	0.919	0.041
		C_{134}	0.002	0.998	0.045
	B_{14}	C_{141}	0.024	0.976	0.044
		C_{142}	0.008	0.992	0.045
		C_{143}	0.057	0.943	0.042
		C_{144}	0.003	0.997	0.045
	B_{15}	C_{151}	0.001	0.999	0.045
		C_{152}	0.047	0.953	0.043
C_{153}		0.045	0.955	0.043	
C_{154}		0.073	0.927	0.042	
C_{155}		0.004	0.996	0.045	

4. Calculation of the weight value of the combination assignment method

According to equation (7), the results of the combined assignment method weights of indicators can be calculated, as shown in Table 10 below.

Table 10 Table of calculation results of weight values of the combined assignment method

Tier 1 indicators (target level)	Secondary indicators (guideline level)	Tertiary indicators (program level)	Calculation results of the weight values of the combined weighting method
A_1	B_{11}	C_{111}	0.040
		C_{112}	0.110
		C_{113}	0.031
		C_{114}	0.192
		C_{115}	0.182
		C_{116}	0.043
	B_{12}	C_{121}	0.227
		C_{122}	0.048
		C_{123}	0.039
		C_{124}	0.085
	B_{13}	C_{131}	0.216
		C_{132}	0.083
		C_{133}	0.228
		C_{134}	0.032
	B_{14}	C_{141}	0.063
C_{142}		0.038	
C_{143}		0.148	
C_{144}		0.033	
B_{15}	C_{151}	0.031	
	C_{152}	0.112	
	C_{153}	0.107	
	C_{154}	0.199	
	C_{155}	0.034	

6.3. Ranking and Analysis of Indicator Importance Results

The relationship between the importance of each indicator is as follows: English teaching design, independent inquiry English learning, English teaching behavior analysis, English independent creativity, English teaching content, English teaching methods, English learning scenario diversification, English teaching context creation, English teaching structure, English teaching process optimization, English collaborative learning, English teaching evaluation, personalized English learning, English continuing willingness to continue learning, English teaching environment, English teaching activities, English learning satisfaction, English strong interactivity, English resource integration, English teaching flexibility, after-school English tutoring, English teaching information presentation, English classroom atmosphere.

7. REFORM MEASURES AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE-ORIENTED ENGLISH TEACHING

We used the G1 entropy value method to calculate the results of the weight values for 23 indicators in this study. In this process, we selected five indicators as key indicators, and the key indicator factors are English teaching design, independent inquiry English learning, English teaching behavior analysis, English autonomous creativity and English teaching content. For these key indicator factors we propose the following five reform measures and suggestions for future English teaching.

- (1) In terms of English teaching design, effective teaching design should be carried out with the study of the discourse as the logical starting point, focusing on the analysis of the interrelationship of all teaching elements, and designing and implementing teaching that unifies goals, activities, and evaluation. We should organize and implement teaching with the concept of English learning activities in order to guide students to enjoy learning and learn well.
- (2) In the area of independent inquiry into English learning, students should set up questions before class or arrange practical tasks for them to learn with a purpose. In the classroom, diversified student-centered English activities are conducted to allow students to take the initiative in thinking and collaborative learning to solve problems, thus cultivating students' autonomy in learning. Virtual English contexts are also created after class so that students can always practice what they have learned, motivating them to take the initiative and learn to apply English naturally from the perspective of enhancing their interest.
- (3) In terms of English teaching behavior, students should be guided to learn and use English in the process of understanding the customs, culture and history of the countries they do not know and broaden their international horizons; to promote the implementation of holistic unit teaching, to organize the teaching contents of each part of speech and plan a series of teaching activities with the unit teaching objectives as a whole, and to enhance the effectiveness of using information technology.
- (4) In terms of independent creativity in English, interactive activities in English should be designed so that students can communicate in stories through virtual characters in different dimensions to complete their learning tasks. In the process, it promotes students to broaden their imagination and thinking space to enhance the creativity of English texts. It also enables them to gradually improve their ability and confidence in speaking English by interacting with virtual characters in English.
- (5) In terms of English teaching content, it should be composed of elements such as English course content themes, discourse, language knowledge, cultural knowledge, language skills and learning strategies. Around these elements, through activities such as learning and understanding, application and practice, transfer and innovation, students' core literacy will be promoted to develop continuously throughout the compulsory education.

8. CONCLUSION

This study provides a new perspective on the evaluation system construction and data analysis for future English teaching quality assessment after the introduction of the metaverse, and thus makes suggestions for future English teaching reform. By analyzing the existing research literature on the application of metaverse and teaching evaluation, we are better able to determine that the application of metaverse in teaching is not yet mature, but it is the general trend. Therefore, in this paper, we combine ideas from other disciplines and use quality function deployment theory to scientifically propose a more comprehensive and richer innovation of educational field architecture to provide greater possibilities for promoting the integration of science and technology with traditional teaching and learning. In order to improve the reliability of the results, we also draw on the G1 entropy method in fuzzy mathematical theory to complete the quantitative analysis of the data in the establishment of the future English teaching quality

evaluation system in our study. Unlike the traditional G1 method, we introduced the identity information weight of experts and the credibility in the part of subjective assignment to improve the reliability and authenticity of the evaluation results in order to enhance the reliability of the final ranking of the importance of evaluation indexes. After deriving the quantitative results of the assessment of the quality of English teaching through quantitative analysis, we selected five key influencing factors based on the importance of the indicators, and targeted five practical suggestions for future English teaching on these five factors to provide a guiding direction for the future improvement of English teaching quality.

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Realization Paths and Countermeasures For Future English Teaching Quality Improvement: A New Systematic Macroscopic Research Perspective

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